

Free-Free Resonant Modes of a Fiber-Reinforced Composite

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ABSTRACT

A procedure for the precise experimental determination of the principal elastic moduli and effective specimen moduli of rectangular section bars, cut from a sheet of orthotropic composite material, is outlined. Free-free resonant bars technique are used throughout, and measured resonant frequencies, together with their associated vibration shapes, are compared with the corresponding data calculated using a finite element transfer matrix technique. Perturbations of the resonant frequencies and vibration shapes due to torsion-flexure coupling are discussed. It is shown that, provided these perturbations are taken into account, measured and calculated values of the resonant modes of a bar of any orientation are in remarkable agreement.

INTRODUCTION

The elastic constants of anisotropic composite materials are important parameters in the design of components and structures. In the first part of this paper a procedure is outlined for the precise determination of the principal elastic moduli and effective specimen moduli necessary to characterize a sheet of a unidirectional fibre reinforced composite. In the second part, finite element calculations which allow the calculation of resonant frequencies, vibration shapes and nodal contours are outlined.

A detailed account of the free-free resonant bar techniques used in this study has been reported in reference [1]. Most previous studies of the elastic moduli of composite specimens have been confined to the fixed-free modes of cantilever specimens or the free-free modes of specimens with weights or inertia members attached (refs. [2] - [5]). Previous studies of elastic moduli using free-free modes by Goggin [6] and Hirai and Kline [7] were confined to the flexural fundamental or low flexural overtones.

Rosinger and Ritchie [8] have demonstrated that in the case of isotropic materials, deviations from the assumed boundary conditions at the fixed ends of cantilever specimens can lead to serious errors in the calculation of dynamic Young's modulus values from the observed flexural resonant frequencies. More serious deviations are expected in the case of composite specimens and these deviations will depend upon the slenderness of the bar and the effectiveness of the end-clamp. In contrast to these deviations, Rosinger et al [9] have shown that all the easily obtainable free-free modes of specimens of an isotropic material are in excellent agreement with the theories of elastic vibrations. In addition, free-free resonant bar techniques allow a more direct determination of the principal shear moduli than is possible from fixed-free modes. However, experimental difficulties inherent in the resonant bar technique [1] are enhanced in the application to anisotropic materials by the presence of mixed modes due to torsion-flexure coupling.

As shown in the second part of this paper, the perturbations of both the resonant frequencies and vibration shapes caused by torsion-flexure coupling can be predicted using a simple finite element calculation. This type of calculation, which separates the inertial and elastic properties of the bar in station and field transfer matrices respectively, was pioneered by Myklestad [10] and extended to a variety of mechanical engineering problems by Pestel and Leckie [11]. More recently Abarcar and Cunniff [3] have shown that both the Timoshenko beam corrections for flexure [12] and Lekhnitskii's theory of static torsion-flexure coupling [13], can be incorporated into the calculations to predict the resonant modes of cantilever specimens. In this paper it is shown that the formulation is easily extended to the calculation of

free-free resonant frequencies, vibration shapes and nodal contours that can be compared with the corresponding experimental results.

PART 1

EXPERIMENTAL DETERMINATION OF THE PRINCIPAL ELASTIC MODULI

1.1 ORTHOTROPIC ELASTICITY

A material which has three orthogonal planes of elastic symmetry at each point is termed elastically orthotropic. The fibre reinforced composite material used in this study was initially assumed to approximate to this symmetry. Taking the axes of coordinates 1, 2 and 3 (see Figure 1), directed perpendicularly to the planes of elastic symmetry, the transformed compliance coefficients, S'_{ij} , referred to the specimen axes, x, y and z, are given by

$$S'_{33} = \frac{1}{E_{zz}} = \frac{\sin^4\theta}{E_{11}} + \frac{\cos^4\theta}{E_{33}} + \left(\frac{1}{G_{13}} - \frac{2\nu_{31}}{E_{33}}\right) \sin^2\theta \cos^2\theta \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} S'_{35} &= 2\left(\frac{\sin^2\theta}{E_{11}} - \frac{\cos^2\theta}{E_{33}}\right) \sin\theta \cos\theta + \left(\frac{1}{G_{13}} - \frac{2\nu_{31}}{E_{33}}\right) (\cos^2\theta - \sin^2\theta) \sin\theta \cos\theta \\ &= \frac{\eta_{zx,zz}}{E_{zz}} = \frac{\eta_{zz,zx}}{G_{xz}} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$S'_{44} = \frac{1}{G_{zy}} = \frac{\cos^2\theta}{G_{23}} + \frac{\sin^2\theta}{G_{12}} \quad (3)$$

$$S'_{55} = \frac{1}{G_{xz}} = \left(\frac{1}{E_{11}} + \frac{1}{E_{33}} + \frac{2\nu_{31}}{E_{33}}\right) \sin^2\theta \cos^2\theta + \frac{1}{G_{13}} (\cos^2\theta - \sin^2\theta)^2 \quad (4)$$

$$S'_{66} = \frac{1}{G_{xy}} = \frac{\sin^2\theta}{G_{23}} + \frac{\cos^2\theta}{G_{12}} \quad (5)$$

These equations are derived in standard texts such as Lekhnitskii [13] and relate the effective specimen moduli, E_{zz} , G_{zy} , G_{xz} and G_{xy} , to the six principal elastic moduli, E_{11} , E_{33} , G_{12} , G_{13} , G_{23} and ν_{31} , needed to characterize a sheet of orthotropic material. The compliance coefficient, S'_{35} , given by equation (2), is related to the specimen moduli, E_{zz} or G_{xz} , by $\eta_{zx,zz}$ or $\eta_{zz,zx}$, the mutual influence coefficients of the first and second kind respectively. Non-zero values of S'_{35} , which occur for $0^\circ < \theta < 90^\circ$, lead to torsion-flexure coupling.

Lekhnitskii [13] has considered the static elastic

response of a cantilever of general anisotropy subjected to the simultaneous action of a bending moment, M , and a torque, T , as shown in Figure 1. For the case of orthotropic symmetry, Lekhnitskii's equations for the deflection, y , and relative angle of twist, $d\phi/dz$, reduce to

$$y = \frac{z^2}{2I_x} (MS'_{33} - \frac{TS'_{35}}{2}) \quad (6)$$

and

$$\frac{d\phi}{dz} = \frac{T}{C_T} - \frac{MS'_{35}}{2I_x} \quad (7)$$

where I_x is the geometrical moment of inertia of the cross-section of the bar with respect to the x -axis, C_T is the generalized torsional rigidity of the bar and S'_{ij} are the compliance coefficients given by equations (1) to (5).

An approximation for C_T which can lead to errors in the calculation of G_{xz} of between 5% and 15% has been quoted and used in some recent papers [3], [5] and [13]. Ritchie and Rosinger [14] have shown that a more precise approximation is given by

$$C_T = \frac{3b}{3} \{1 + F a/b\} / \{S'_{55} + F \frac{(S'_{35})^2}{S'_{33}} \frac{a}{b}\} \quad (8)$$

where

$$F = -0.6274 \left(\frac{S'_{44}}{S'_{55}} \right)^{1/2} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (2n+1)^{-5} \tanh \left\{ \left(\frac{2n+1}{2} \right) \frac{\pi b}{a} \left(\frac{S'_{55}}{S'_{44}} \right)^{1/2} \right\} \quad (9)$$

a is the thickness of the bar and b its width. For the 0° and 90° bars, equations (8) and (9) reduce to the equation derived by Love [15] for the special case of an anisotropic material with a two-fold axis parallel to the specimen axis. This is the case for both the 0° and 90° bars of an orthotropic material. Fortunately the infinite series in equation (9) converges very rapidly for the values of a/b and S'_{44}/S'_{55} of practical interest and C_T can be rapidly evaluated by computer.

It is assumed throughout this study that these static descriptions of torsion-flexure coupling and the torsional rigidity of a rectangular section bar of orthotropic symmetry can be used without modification to describe a beam subjected to dynamic bending moments and torques.

1.2 MATERIAL, SPECIMENS AND EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

The sheet of composite material used in this investigation

consisted of a calcium carbonate filled polyester matrix, reinforced with unidirectional glass fibres. The results presented below and the calculations presented in Part 2 were obtained for seven carefully machined rectangular section bars in which the unidirectional fibres are at nominal angles of 0° , 15° , 30° , 45° , 60° , 75° and 90° to the longitudinal axis of the specimen. It is estimated that for the 0° and 90° bars the error in θ is $< \pm 1/4^\circ$ while for the other bars the error in θ is $\pm 1/2^\circ$. The average density of the material, as determined from the mass and dimensions of each bar was found to be $1.970 \pm 0.005 \text{ g.cm}^{-3}$.

A block diagram of the instrumentation used in this investigation is shown in Figure 2. With the exception of the optical displacement transducer the equipment is standard for resonant bar techniques. Resonance is induced in a typical specimen via a fine wire coupling attached to a piezoelectric transducer driven by an audio oscillator. The non-contacting optical transducer serves as pick-up transducer and can be used to scan across the surface of the vibrating specimen. In this way it is possible to map the vibration shape with a resolution of better than $2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}$, and hence index the vibration mode.

More detailed descriptions of the experimental techniques, instrumentation and the mapping of vibration shapes are given in [1] and [9]. In addition to the fundamentals of flexure and torsion all the easily obtainable overtones of each of the mode types were also investigated. Maximum peak to peak surface displacements of the vibrating specimens were less than $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}$ for the fundamental modes and considerably less than this value for the overtones. All the experimental determinations were carried out at ambient temperature.

For most specimens, the fundamental of torsion together with the first two or three overtones were easily obtained. Experimental frequencies were measured to the nearest 0.1 Hz and provided that care was taken in the positioning of nodal supports for repeated determinations, reproducibility was found to be within $\pm 1.0 \text{ Hz}$ for resonant frequencies up to 5 kHz. In flatwise-flexure, the fundamental and first four or five overtones were measured for most specimens. The experimental resonant frequencies for the 0° , 45° and 90° bars are indexed in Tables 1, 2 and 3 respectively.

1.3 DETERMINATION OF THE PRINCIPAL MODULI

The methods of calculating the principal Young's moduli involve an iterative procedure which starts with estimates obtained from the simple Bernoulli-Euler theory of bending. These estimates are then refined in successive iterations according to the Timoshenko beam theory.

TABLE 1

COMPARISON OF THE EXPERIMENTAL AND CALCULATED RESONANT FREQUENCIES FOR THE 0° BAR*

MODE	EXPERIMENTAL		CALCULATED ⁺	
	f_n Hz	(f_n/f_1) F,T	f_n Hz	(f_n/f_1) F,T
1 F	333.7	1.00	337.7	1.00
2 F	926.7	2.74	927.8	2.75
1 T	1434.8	1.00	1434.8	1.00
3 F	1812.3	5.37	1809.6	5.36
4 F	2979.1	8.82	2971.0	8.80
5 F	4411.1	13.06	4400.1	13.03
6 F	6104.8	18.08	6083.5	18.02

* SPECIMEN DIMENSIONS 21.008 cm x 1.696 cm x 0.333 cm
MASS 23.435 g

+ 64 Stations

TABLE 2

COMPARISON OF THE EXPERIMENTAL AND CALCULATED RESONANT FREQUENCIES FOR THE 45° BAR*

MODE	EXPERIMENTAL		CALCULATED ⁺	
	f_n Hz	(f_n/f_1) F,T	f_n Hz	(f_n/f_1) F,T
1 F	767.9	1.00	767.5	1.00
2 F	2091.9	2.72	2101.6	2.74
3 F	4155.9	5.41	4066.9	5.30
1 T	4524.7	1.00	4483.6	1.00
4 F	6762.7	8.81	6649.4	8.66
2 T	9057.6	2.00	8949.0	2.00
5 F	10006.0	13.03	9779.0	12.74
3 T	13753.7	3.04	13410.5	2.99
6 F	13836.4	18.02	13421.1	17.49
4 T	18316.5	4.05	17896.1	3.99
5 T	23010.9	5.09	22378.2	4.99

* SPECIMEN DIMENSIONS 11.179 cm x 1.270 cm x 0.338 cm
MASS 9.448 g

+ 64 Stations

1.3.1 Initial Values of Young's Moduli E_{11} and E_{33}

Initial estimates of the principal Young's moduli E_{11} and E_{33} were obtained from measurements of the fundamental of flatwise-

TABLE 3

COMPARISON OF THE EXPERIMENTAL AND CALCULATED RESONANT FREQUENCIES FOR THE 90° BAR*

MODE	EXPERIMENTAL		CALCULATED ⁺	
	f _n Hz	(f _n /f ₁) _{F,T}	f _n Hz	(f _n /f ₁) _{F,T}
1 F	731.2	1.00	731.5	1.00
2 F	1994.8	2.73	2005.8	2.74
1 T	3533.4	1.00	3533.1	1.00
3 F	3901.5	5.34	3901.8	5.33
4 F	6315.7	8.64	6384.4	8.73
2 T	7030.5	1.99	7064.1	2.00
5 F	9317.8	12.74	9419.3	12.88
3 T	10573.5	2.99	10590.9	3.00

* SPECIMEN DIMENSIONS 11.180 cm x 1.268 cm x 0.337 cm
 MASS 9.392.g

+ 64 Stations

flexure, f_{1F} , on the 90° and 0° bars respectively. In the following, resonant frequencies are denoted by f_{nF} or f_{nT} , where n is the mode number while F and T refer to flatwise-flexural and torsional mode types respectively. For long slender bars, Young's modulus is related to the fundamental of flatwise-flexure, f_{1F} , by the simple (Bernoulli-Euler) equation

$$E = 0.94645 \rho \left[\frac{\ell^2 f_{1F}^2}{a} \right]^2 \quad (10)$$

where a is the thickness of the bar, ℓ the length and ρ the density of the material. This value must be corrected for the effects of transverse displacements due to shear and rotatory inertia. As shown in [9], these corrections can be carried out for an isotropic material using Huang's frequency equation [16] for a Timoshenko beam provided the value of E/KG is known. The value of the shear coefficient, K , has been shown to be very close to 5/6 for a stainless steel [1] and a silicon carbide [9]. The same value is assumed to apply to the composite material used in this study. For orthotropic materials, Nowinski [17] has shown that E/KG must be replaced by E_{zz}/KG_{zy} . Consequently, initial estimates for $G_{zy} = G_{23}$ for the 0° bar, and $G_{zy} = G_{12}$ for the 90° bar, are required before the initial estimates for E_{33} and E_{11} can be refined.

1.3.2 Poisson's Ratio, ν_{31} , and Shear Modulus G_{13}

ν_{31} was calculated from the lateral and longitudinal

strains measured from strain gauges during tensile tests on two separate 0° bars. The average value obtained was found to be 0.300. Using this value of ν_{31} , together with the initial values of E_{33} , E_{ZZ} for the 45° bar and E_{11} , allows the determination of an initial value for G_{13} using equation (1). This procedure is possible (ignoring Timoshenko corrections to E_{ij}), since, as shown in Table 2, the fundamental of flatwise-flexure used to determine $E_{ZZ}(45^\circ)$ is far removed from the fundamental of torsion. Consequently, according to the calculations of Brown [18] and Hearmon [19], the effect of torsion-flexure coupling on the fundamental of flexure is negligible in this case. This was confirmed experimentally by the absence of measureable torsional distortion in the vibration shape of the fundamental of flatwise-flexure.

In principle, a dynamic value of ν_{31} can be measured by recording longitudinal and lateral amplitudes during longitudinal resonance of a 0° bar. These amplitudes can be monitored using two of the optical sensors described in section 1.2. However, for the longitudinal strain amplitudes used in this study the lateral amplitudes were too small to measure with sufficient precision. Consequently, the static value of ν_{31} has been assumed to be correct and is held constant throughout the iterative procedure described below.

1.3.3 Initial Values of the Shear Moduli G_{12} and G_{23}

According to the Timoshenko beam theory, the ratios of the frequencies of flatwise-flexure, f_{nF}/f_{1F} , depend on a/l and E_{zz}/KG_{zy} . Values of f_{nF}/f_{1F} can be calculated from Huang's frequency equation as described in [9]. Thus, if E_{zz} is known, G_{zy} can be varied until a set of calculated values of f_{nF}/f_{1F} corresponds with the set of f_{nF}/f_{1F} found experimentally. If this procedure is carried out for the 0° and 90° bars, values of G_{23} and G_{12} are found respectively. This is the method used in reference [3]. However, to obtain good values of E_{33} and E_{11} , long slender bars are required, as shown in [9]. For such bars, the Timoshenko corrections can be neglected in the calculation of Young's modulus from the fundamental of flatwise-flexure. Consequently, a large number of f_{nF}/f_{1F} ratios must be accurately determined experimentally in order to obtain accurate G_{ij} values by this method. A discussion of the probable errors in the E/KG ratios determined by this technique is contained in [2] where it is shown that for $E/G < 10$ and the specimen dimensions used in this study, it would be necessary to determine resonant frequencies out to high mode numbers ($\nu n = 20$) in order to obtain a reasonable accuracy of $\pm 10\%$ in the value of E/G .

A more direct method has been developed in this study where values of G_{12} and G_{23} are obtained from the torsional fundamental resonant frequencies of 90° and 0° bars respectively. Calculation of the shear modulus, G , of a material can be carried

out using the following equation.

$$f_{nT} = \frac{n}{2\lambda} \left(\frac{C_T}{I_P} \right)^{1/2} \quad (11)$$

where f_{nT} is the resonant frequency for torsional mode number n , I_P is the polar moment of inertia per unit length of the specimen and C_T is the generalized torsional rigidity of the bar, given by equations (8) and (9). Since $S_{55} = 1/G_{13}$ for both the 0° and 90° bars, equations (8), (9) and (11) can be used to determine $G_{23} = 1/S_{44}$ from the fundamental of torsion for the 0° bar, and $G_{12} = 1/S_{44}$ from the fundamental of torsion of the 90° bar.

Using the initial estimates of G_{12} and G_{23} calculated as described above, an initial estimate of G_{zy} for the 45° bar can be calculated using equation (4). The values of these initial estimates are listed in column 2 of Table 4.

TABLE 4
EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS FOR THE PRINCIPAL
MODULI

MODULUS GNm ⁻²	INITIAL VALUE	FIRST ITERATION	SECOND ITERATION
E ₃₃ (0°)	37.41	37.52	37.53
E ₁₁ (90°)	13.67	33.77	13.77
E _{zz} (45°)	15.02	15.12	15.12
G ₁₃	5.478	5.516	5.517
G ₁₂	6.666	6.231	6.214
G ₂₃	6.030	5.500	5.480
v ₃₁	0.300	0.300	0.300

1.3.4 Iterative Refinement of the Principal Moduli

With the initial values of E_{zz} and G_{ij} for the 0° , 45° and 90° bars listed in Table 4, the E_{zz} values can be recalculated using the initial values of E_{zz}/KG_{zy} in the Timoshenko beam theory. The resulting values of E_{zz} are listed in column 3 of Table 4. These new values of E_{zz} yield a new value of G_{13} by the method described in section 1.3.2 above and, subsequently, lead to new values of G_{12} and G_{23} with the procedure described in section 1.3.3. The whole procedure is then repeated until two successive sets of moduli are essentially unchanged. As shown in Table 4, the procedure converges very rapidly. The final refined values of the principal moduli used in the subsequent calculations and in the finite element calculations in Part 2 are listed in the right hand column of Table 4.

1.4 RESULTS

The main results of this study consist of the principal moduli listed in Table 4 and a comparison of the experimental values of E_{ZZ} vs θ and G_{XZ} vs θ with the corresponding theoretical equations (1) and (4), respectively, for an orthotropic material. These results are summarized in Figures 3 and 4.

E_{ZZ} values calculated from the fundamental of flexure are within 1% of the values calculated by equation (1). From the method of determination, the experimental points for the fundamental of flexure are forced to fit at 0° , 45° and 90° . Deviations from the theoretical curve are first noticeable for the second overtone of flexure, as shown in Figure 3. The deviation is a maximum of about 3% and can be traced to coupling between the fundamental of torsion and the second overtone of flexure as described in Part 2.

Assuming that G_{ZY} for each specimen can be calculated by inserting the final values of G_{12} and G_{23} in equation (3), G_{XZ} for each specimen can be calculated from the fundamental of torsion using equations (8), (9) and (11). These experimental results are compared with the theoretical curve for $1/S_{55}$ for an orthotropic composite, which is given by equation (4) and the full curve in Figure 4. The methods described above force a fit at 0° and 90° . Deviation of the experimental points in the range $\theta = 15^\circ$ to $\theta = 45^\circ$ is due to torsion-flexure coupling. The maximum deviation occurs for the 30° bar and amounts to about 14%. Quantitative calculations of the effects of torsion-flexure coupling are described in Part 2, together with the effects of torsion-flexure coupling on the vibration modes of the specimens. In addition, it is shown that the coupled flexural modes are approximately 'free' while the coupled torsional modes are approximately 'pure'. This effect was first pointed out and demonstrated on specimens of wood by Hearmon [19].

PART 2

PREDICTION OF RESONANT FREQUENCIES AND NODAL CONTOURS

2.1 TRANSFER MATRIX TECHNIQUE

The model of the beam used in this study consists of two half-fields of length $\Delta z/2$, one at each end of the beam and $N-1$ fields of length Δz separated by N masses concentrated at N points called stations. Each station contains mass $m_i = \mu \ell / N$ where μ is the mass per unit length of the beam of length ℓ . Each field is treated as a massless Timoshenko beam containing all the bending stiffness and torsional rigidities of the system.

Derivation of the field and station transfer matrices for

isotropic materials is given in detail by Pestel and Leckie [11]. The extension to orthotropic materials has been outlined by Abarcar and Cunniff [3] and Ritchie et al [20] have given a more detailed treatment including an assessment of the approximations involved. The final equation can be written as

$$[S]_{N+1} = [T_F]_{\beta=\frac{1}{2}} [T_S] \prod_{i=1}^{N-1} \{ [T_F]_{\beta=1} [T_S] \}_i [T_F]_{\beta=\frac{1}{2}} [S]_0 \quad (12)$$

where

$$[T_S]_i = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{-m_i \omega^2 \Delta z_i}{E_{zz} A} & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{-m_i \omega^2 \Delta z_i^3}{E_{zz} I_x} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -I_{pi} \frac{\omega^2 \Delta z_i S'_{35}}{2 I_x} & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

and

$$[T_F]_i = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \beta & 0 & \frac{\beta^2}{2} & \left(\frac{\beta E_{zz} I_x}{K G_{zy} A (\Delta z_i)^2} \frac{-\beta^3}{6} \right) & \frac{-\beta^2}{2} \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & \beta & \frac{-\beta^2}{2} & \beta \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & \frac{-\beta E_{zz} S'_{35}}{2} & \frac{\beta^2 E_{zz} S'_{35}}{4} & \frac{-2\beta I_x}{C_T S'_{35}} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & -\beta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

are the dimensionless forms of the station and field transfer matrices respectively. In the station transfer matrix, A is the cross-sectional area of the bar and ω is the radian frequency of the resonant vibrations. In the field transfer matrix, $\beta = 1$ for a full field and $\beta = \frac{1}{2}$ for the half fields at each end of the bar. Since $[S]_0$ and $[S]_{N+1}$ are the state vectors at each end of the bar, the boundary conditions for free-free modes can be stated as follows:

$$[S]_0 = \begin{bmatrix} y' = y'_0 \\ \psi' = \psi'_0 \\ \phi' = \phi'_0 \\ M' = 0 \\ V' = 0 \\ T' = 0 \end{bmatrix}_0 \quad \text{and} \quad [S]_{N+1} = \begin{bmatrix} |y'| = y'_0 \\ |\psi'| = \psi'_0 \\ |\phi'| = \phi'_0 \\ M' = 0 \\ V' = 0 \\ T' = 0 \end{bmatrix}_{N+1} \quad (15)$$

where ψ' and ϕ' are the angles of bending and twisting respectively. M' , V' and T' are the dimensionless bending moment, shear force and torque respectively. The possibility of both symmetrical and anti-symmetrical modes is indicated by the absolute values $|y'|$, $|\psi'|$ and $|\phi'|$.

2.2 CALCULATION OF RESONANT FREQUENCIES AND NORMAL MODE SHAPES

2.2.1 Resonant Frequencies

For convenience, equation (12) can be written in the form

$$[S]_{N+1} = [B] [S]_0 \quad (16)$$

where $[B]$ is the six by six 'beam matrix'. Equation (16) only holds if

$$\det \begin{bmatrix} B_{41} & B_{42} & B_{43} \\ B_{51} & B_{52} & B_{53} \\ B_{61} & B_{62} & B_{63} \end{bmatrix} = 0 \quad (17)$$

and, therefore, the above condition replaces the frequency equation in the simple formulation of the vibration of isotropic beams.

Values of the natural resonant frequencies, ω_n , corresponding to the zeros of the above determinant can be rapidly calculated by numerical techniques. Choosing the number of beam elements to be 2^{a+1} where a is an integer, allows the rapid determination of $N-1$

$\Pi \{ [T_F]_{\beta=1} [T_S]_i \}$ by repeated squaring. However, when vibration

shapes must be calculated, repeated squaring cannot be used and the method of shifted matrix multiplication described by Pestel and Leckie [11] is used to reduce computation time.

2.2.2 Vibration Shapes

To compute the generalized displacements y'_i , ψ'_i , and ϕ'_i at

each station and, hence, the vibration shape for each natural frequency, $[S]_0$, the state vector at one end of the bar, must be known. However, it is only necessary to specify y'_0 and the obvious choice is $y'_0=1$. Then

$$\begin{bmatrix} B_{41} & B_{42} & B_{43} \\ B_{51} & B_{52} & B_{53} \\ B_{61} & B_{62} & B_{63} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ \psi'_0 \\ \phi'_0 \end{bmatrix} = 0 \quad (18)$$

and therefore, ψ'_0 and ϕ'_0 can be determined. Thus, starting from one end of the bar the generalized displacements can be calculated at successive stations by shifted matrix multiplication. The resulting vibration shape can be plotted by computer or displayed on a display screen as outlined below.

2.3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

2.3.1 Resonant Frequencies

Calculated torsional (f_{nT}) and flatwise-flexural (f_{nF}) resonant frequencies have been compared with the corresponding experimental values for all seven bars. Results for three representative bars are listed in Tables 1, 2 and 3. Indexing of these modes for both the experimental and calculated resonant frequencies was carried out with reference to the measured and calculated nodal contours respectively, as described in the next section.

As expected, the best agreement between the observed and calculated frequency spectra occurs for the 0° and 90° bars (see Tables 1 and 3). This is because for these bars $S'_{35} = 0$ and the calculations are, essentially, the same as those for an isotropic bar. For the first four modes, the agreement between the observed and calculated resonant frequencies is very good for all seven bars. For these 28 modes, the average percentage difference between observed and calculated resonant frequencies is only 0.6% with a maximum difference of 2.5% for f_{3F} on the 15° bar.

Although there is some divergence between the experimental and calculated resonant frequencies for the higher overtones, the ratios $(f_n/f_1)_{F,T}$ for the two different mode types, as determined from the experimental and calculated frequencies, are in good agreement. Besides possible experimental errors in the measured values of θ and the experimental uncertainty in the determination of the resonant frequencies, warping of the cross-section, which is neglected in the transfer matrix calculations, becomes more important for the higher overtones. In addition, slightly improved agreement between observed and calculated frequencies for the

higher overtones can be obtained by increasing the number of stations [20].

2.3.2 Vibration Shapes

The calculated vibration shapes for f_{1T} and f_{3F} in the 30° bar are shown in Figures 5 and 6 respectively. In Figure 5(a) the generalized displacements y' , ψ' and ϕ' are plotted as a function of the fractional displacement z/l from one end of the bar. In Figure 5(b) a two dimensional projection of the data has been plotted by computer. Corresponding results for the next highest frequency are shown in Figures 6(a) and 6(b) respectively. From these diagrams it can easily be seen that Figure 5 represents a predominantly torsional mode, while Figure 6 represents a predominantly flexural mode. In addition, evidence of the coupling between these modes is apparent in the pronounced flexural component in Figure 5 and the slight torsional component in Figure 6.

Although vibration shapes similar to those shown in Figures 5(b) and 6(b) can be laboriously mapped out experimentally by the methods described in [1], this procedure is neither necessary nor desirable. Since the value of y' , ψ' and ϕ' can be calculated at each station, the corresponding displacement and rotations of the cross-section at that point can be used to determine points of zero displacement on the periphery of the cross-section. These points trace out the nodal contours of the vibration shapes and can be compared with the nodal contours mapped experimentally. This comparison for the data in Figures 5 and 6 is made in Figure 7. Experimentally mapped nodal contours are shown in Figure 7(a). As shown in Figure 7, good quantitative agreement was obtained for these coupled modes. For the lower uncoupled flexural modes, calculated nodal contours were also in good quantitative agreement with the measured results. Any differences between the calculated and measured vibration shapes for the coupled modes is attributed to measurable warping of the specimen cross-section, which is not explicitly included in the transfer matrix calculation. The nodal contours shown in Figure 7 are very similar to those reported by Clary [21] for the free-free modes of laminated panels.

Besides using the transfer matrix technique to predict the vibration spectra of anisotropic bars, the precalculation of vibration shapes of θ° bars can be an invaluable aid in the experimental determinations. For example, the precalculation of the vibration shape indicates positions for the nodal support wires so that the mode can be easily generated with minimum damping.

Details of the computer programs written for this study will be reported elsewhere.

2.3.3 Torsion-Flexure Coupling

By definition, S_{33} is the constant which relates an applied

normal stress to the response, which for non-zero values of S'_{35} , will consist of a combination of normal and shear strains. Similarly S'_{55} relates an applied shear stress to a combination of normal and shear strains. Because these constants relate free responses to specific stresses, the corresponding moduli $(E_F)_{zz}$ and $(G_F)_{xz}$ have been termed 'free' moduli by Voigt [22]. Thus,

$$(E_F)_{zz} = 1/S'_{33} \text{ and } (G_F)_{xz} = 1/S'_{55} \quad (19)$$

where S'_{33} and S'_{55} are the specimen compliances given by equations (1) and (4). 'Pure' moduli, $(E_p)_{zz}$ and $(G_p)_{xz}$, which correspond to the simultaneous application of normal and shear stresses such that the response in the case of $(E_p)_{zz}$ is a pure normal strain, while in the case of $(G_p)_{xz}$, the response is a pure shear strain, were also defined by Voigt [22]. Under these circumstances,

$$(E_p)_{zz} = (1/S'_{33}) (1 - \eta_{zx,zz} \eta_{zz,zx})^{-1} \quad (20)$$

and

$$(G_p)_{xz} = (1/S'_{55}) (1 - \eta_{zx,zz} \eta_{zz,zx})^{-1} \quad (21)$$

where $\eta_{zx,zz}$ and $\eta_{zz,zx}$ are the coefficients of mutual influence of the 1st and 2nd kind defined by equation (2). These definitions of the free and pure moduli are particularly useful in the discussion of torsion-flexure coupling, and more importantly, experiments can sometimes be devised which yield only the pure or free moduli. In resonant bar experiments on specimens with non-zero values of S'_{35} , the response is neither pure nor free.

The perturbations of resonant frequencies, and hence, effective specimen moduli due to torsion-flexure coupling have been theoretically investigated by Goens [23], Brown [18] and Hearmon [19]. The approximate theory of Hearmon [19] and [24] yields the useful rule that the frequencies split such that predominantly flexural modes are approximately free while the predominantly torsional modes are approximately pure. In Figures 3 and 4 the specimen moduli calculated from the experimental resonant frequencies and the resonant frequencies generated by the finite calculations, are compared with the theoretical curves for the free and pure moduli. As can be seen from Figure 3 the effective Young's modulus as a function of θ , determined from f_{3F} , is closer to the 'free' curve than the 'pure' curve. In contrast, the data of Figure 4 show that the measured and calculated shear moduli, determined from the measured and calculated values of f_{1T} respectively, are in reasonably good agreement with the pure curve.

The approximate nature of this rule is demonstrated in Figure 4 where it can be seen that the experimental and finite element values are in good agreement with each other, but still deviate by as much as 4% (for the 30° and 60° bars) from the pure

curve. The reason for maximum perturbations around 30° and 60° can be seen in Figure 8. In this figure, the ratios f_{3F}/f_{1F} and f_{1T}/f_{1F} generated using the principal elastic moduli given in Table 4 and the finite element calculations outlined above, are compared with the experimental values. In addition, the vibration shapes for each angle can be generated by computer. These show that at two particular angles, 31.5° and 67.5° , the vibration shapes for f_{3F} and f_{1T} become indistinguishable, while to either side of these angles, the vibration shapes can be indexed as predominantly torsional or flexural as indicated in Figure 8. In the absence of coupling (i.e. $S'_{35} = 0$) it is possible for f_{3F} and f_{1T} to become identical, then the curves shown in Figure 8 would simply intersect without perturbation of the resonant frequencies. Figure 8 is, in essence, a demonstration of the universal non-crossing rule for coupled oscillators, which forbids the tuning of coupled oscillators to the same frequency.

Other workers have demonstrated torsion-flexure coupling in anisotropic materials. Hearmon [18] has shown that the fixed-free modes of plywood produce approximately free Young's modulus values and approximately pure shear modulus values. In addition, Hearmon [23] has shown that cantilevers of plywood subjected to relatively large end loads produce visible twisting as well as bending. More recently, Abarcar and Cunniff [3] have revealed the Chladni figures of coupled fixed-free modes of fibre-reinforced composites using chalk powder. Others, including Clary [21], Clary and Cooper [4] and Adams and Bacon [5] have presented evidence of torsion-flexure coupling in cantilever and free-free specimens.

Brown [17] has pointed out that coupling is restricted to symmetric modes or antisymmetric modes and is a maximum for mode types with the same mode number. The geometry of the specimens used in this study preclude the possibility of f_{1F} approaching f_{1T} . Consequently, the coupling reported here between f_{3F} and f_{1T} is relatively weak. Nevertheless, the coupling produces easily measurable perturbations of the resonant frequencies and gross distortion of the vibration shapes. The results shown in Figures 7 and 8 clearly demonstrate that torsion-flexure coupling cannot be neglected on the grounds that the geometry is chosen so that the fundamentals of torsion and flexure are well separated.

CONCLUSIONS

The main conclusions reached in these papers are as follows:

- (1) The fundamental and overtones of vibration of a composite material vibrating in flatwise-flexural or torsional modes can be precisely determined using free-free resonant bar techniques.

(2) The resonant frequencies of a 0° bar, a 90° bar and a bar of one other orientation can be used to determine the principal moduli necessary to characterize a sheet of material of orthotropic or higher symmetry.

(3) Even for b/a ratios >3 the approximation most frequently used [13] for the generalized torsional rigidity of an orthotropic material is not sufficiently accurate for precise determination of the specimen shear modulus G_{xz} . A more precise approximation is given by equations (8) and (9).

(4) Specimen moduli E_{zz} and G_{xz} can be determined for bars of any orientation θ from their flatwise-flexural and torsional resonant frequencies respectively.

(5) Discrepancies between the experimental values of E_{zz} and G_{xz} and the corresponding theoretical values of $1/S_{33}$ and $1/S_{55}$ for θ bars can be correlated with mixed vibration shapes due to torsion-flexure coupling.

(6) The transfer matrix technique can be used to predict accurately the free-free resonant frequencies of rectangular section bars of composite materials of orthotropic or higher symmetry.

(7) Static descriptions of torsion-flexure coupling and of torsional rigidity incorporated into dynamic calculations have been justified experimentally at least for the fundamentals and lower overtones.

(8) Nodal contours can be calculated easily and compared with experimental maps of zero displacement amplitude.

(9) Even relatively weak torsion-flexure coupling between f_{1T} and f_{3F} leads to measurable perturbations of the resonant frequencies and vibration shapes.

(10) Discrepancies between G_{xz} values calculated from experimental f_{1T} values and the curve $1/S_{55}$ vs θ (equation (4)) have been confirmed by the transfer matrix calculations.

(11) Hearmon's rule that coupled modes occur with the flexural modes approximately free and the torsional modes approximately pure has been confirmed for the weak coupling between the free-free modes f_{3F} and f_{1T} .

(12) The non-crossing rule for the coupled vibrations has been demonstrated.

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Fig.1. Cantilever subjected to the joint action of bending and twisting moments and showing the relationship between the principal axes 1, 2 and 3 and the specimen axes x, y and z for a θ° bar.

Fig.2. Block diagram of the resonant bar instrumentation showing the configuration for mapping the vibration shape of the fundamental of flatwise flexure.

Fig.3. Comparison of the measured and calculated values of E_{ZZ} with the theoretical curves for the free and pure Young's modulus.

Fig.4. Comparison of the measured and calculated values of G_{XZ} with the theoretical curves for the free and pure shear modulus.

Fig. 5. (a) Generalized displacements $y'(z)$, $\psi'(z)$, $\phi'(z)$ (shown by \circ , \square , and \times respectively) for the third mode (f_{1T}) of the 30° bar. (b) Projection of the vibration shape.

Fig. 6. (a) Generalized displacements $y'(z)$, $\psi'(z)$, $\phi'(z)$ (shown by \circ , \square , and \times respectively) for the fourth mode (f_{3P}) of the 30° bar. (b) Projection of the vibration shape.

Fig.7. (a) Nodal contours of f_{3F} and f_{1T} measured experimentally on the 30° bar. (b) Nodal contours of f_{3F} and f_{1T} calculated for the 30° bar.

Fig.8. Illustration of the non-crossing rule for the coupled frequencies f_{3F} and f_{1F} .

DISCUSSION/Session 7

QUESTION: W.R. Hoover, Sandia Labs, Albuquerque, New Mexico

What fracture processes are occurring in B/Al at the very low stress levels at which original acoustic emission begins?

ANSWER: A.P. Grenis, Army Materials and Mechanics Research Center Watertown, Massachusetts

The processes are not known. The authors have determined that unreinforced Al does not give the same type of acoustical emission as the composite. Thus, the observed emissions are attributed to some phenomenon associated with the presence of the reinforcing fibers, however, this is not necessarily fiber fracture.

QUESTION: W.R. Hoover

What thickness spec. did you use? Hancock has shown that the plane stress to plane strain transition occurs between 0.090" and 0.100". Thus the toughness of specimens below this level would be expected to be a function of thickness. Above the transition $K \neq f(B)$.

ANSWER: K.N. Street, Corbeil-Essonnes, France

The specimens went up to 20 layers in thickness which is about 0.14".

QUESTION: M.R. Piggot, University of Toronto

Have you tried to explain the values of energy dissipated, which you have observed, by the use of my formulation?

ANSWER: S.J. Burden, Drexel University, Philadelphia, Pennsylvania

No. the mechanism of energy adsorption in our ductile matrix composites was the plastic deformation of the fibers and the matrix. Fiber pull-out did not adsorb a significant amount of energy.

COMMENT: M.A. Wright

(re: paper by J.M. Grandemange and K.N. Street) In agreement with the work reported, we have found that the fracture of centre notched B/Al specimens can be described by using a critical stress intensity approach. These results are described in the paper by Wright and Ianuzzi reported in Failure Modes in Composites II published by the Metallurgical Society of AIME.

In addition, it may be instructive to note the results that a student of mine, H. Kulkarni, obtained when he applied the finite element technique to a study of the deformation of a centre-notched B/Al composite specimen. Fig. 1 illustrates the deformation patterns that result when a fixed displacement of 0.001 is applied at a distance of 0.6 inches from the center notch. As can be seen, the lines of constant displacement are reasonably spaced and evenly distributed across the specimen. The inscribed lines, originally straight across the specimen before the displacement, indicate the extent of distortion of the specimen after loading, particularly near the crack. In this case, the displacement was not sufficient to introduce any plasticity into the matrix. In contrast, increasing the displacement by a factor of four resulted in the displacement geometry becoming dependent on the extent of matrix plasticity. For instance, the constant displacement and inscribed lines indicated in Fig. 2 resulted if the deformation in both the matrix and fiber of the composite were completely elastic. However, as shown in Fig. 3, if the matrix deforms plastically, most of the displacement occurs in the matrix at the crack tip along a line almost parallel to the fiber axis. In this instance, the face of the machined slot appears to move almost rigidly, very little shear takes place. An approximate description of the failure mode might then involve a treatment of the crack using the concept of a "Super Fiber," the diameter of which is equal to the total crack length. The criteria for crack extension could then be the failure of those fibers that make up a linear bundle distributed along the tip of the machined slot. The length of the bundle would be given by the ineffective length associated with the Super Fibers. Notwithstanding, the extent of the deformation at the crack tip might explain the observation of Grandemange and Street that the k_c values do not vary with

notch root radius.

The following questions and comments were addressed to M.J. Owen, University of Nottingham.

QUESTION: P. Scala, Cortland, New York

Is this a prepreg?

ANSWER:

No, this is dry layup.

QUESTION: P. Scala

What are typical applications?

ANSWER:

Large tanks for solid and liquid containment.

QUESTION: K.E. Hofer, Jr., IIT Research Institute, Chicago, Ill.

Would you comment on why there is a smaller difference at lower glass contents (where one would expect the resin differences to show up) than there is at higher glass contents where resin differences would be less important. Is this related to the tubular configuration?

ANSWER:

The major difference between materials appears to correlate with a change in the raw material production location.

QUESTION: R.N. Kelly, Bedford, Massachusetts

I thought I noticed some evidence of bubbles in your last few micrographs. Were these the nucleus for cracks?

Also, were your tests at room temperature only, specifically, did you conduct tests below the glass transition temperature of the matrix?

ANSWER:

The bubbles tended to occur on the resin rich surface layer, but there was no evidence to suggest that they acted as crack nuclei.

All testing was carried out at room temperature, i.e. below the glass transition temperature of its matrix.

QUESTION: M. Hamstad, Lawrence Livermore Lab., Livermore, Cal.

What was the rate of cycling of the fatigue test, and the shape of the internal pressure pulse?

ANSWER:

The rate of cycling was 100 cycles/minute, and the shape a truncated sine curve.

QUESTION: K.N. Street, Corbeil-Essonnes, France

In service, fatigue failure of internally pressurized tubular structures generally means leakage, weeping, etc. You did not attempt to allow this to occur in your work. How, therefore, did you quantify your criteria of matrix cracking, the onset of fibre debonding and so on?

ANSWER:

The onset of fibre debonding and matrix cracking were assessed by visual observation. Debonding in an unlined cylinder is visible against the oil background. The laminate takes on a slightly milky appearance during the loaded part of the cycle which disappears during the unloaded part of the cycle. As debonding develops this becomes more permanent. Resin cracking can be observed against the background of the black liner. The first few resin cracks strongly reflect light from an inspection lamp. Thus the criterion is the observation of the number of cycles at which the first signs of debonding or resin cracking are observed.

The following questions and comments were addressed to T.T. Chiao, University of California, Livermore, Cal.

QUESTION: B. Riseborough, Fiberglas Canada Ltd., Guelph, Ontario

Re: testing of fiber composite materials. How has the problem of nonuniformity in the elongated NOL ring test specimen been overcome?

ANSWER:

By changes in geometry by making flat sides.

QUESTION: B. Riseborough

No mention was made of the rail shear test. Could the speaker please comment on this test?

ANSWER:

There has been difficulty in data interpretation.

QUESTION: D. Kim, Westinghouse Electric R&D Center, Pittsburgh

Elastic modulus and strength from tubular specimen in fiber direction and transverse direction are generally in good agreement with those from coupon specimen from the same prepreg and fiber volume but Poisson's ratio are not in our experience. What is your comment?

ANSWER:

Insufficient data are available. Comment was made on the need for gages located both on the inner and outer specimen surfaces.

QUESTION: T. Alts, Institute for Theoretical Physice, Aachem, West Germany

The compliance matrix or the stiffness matrix, respectively, are only symmetric if the stress tensor is symmetric and if an elastic or viscoelastic energy with certain properties against time reversal exist.

ANSWER:

Author agrees.

QUESTION: T. Alts

The tensor notation of the stress-strain relation should be preferred over the contracted notation, since coordinate transformations can easily be handled.

ANSWER:

Author contends the contracted notation is easier for materials engineers to use because, in particular, the factor of 2 difference with engineering notation is removed.

QUESTION: T. Alts

The use of a tensile test at a 45° reinforced sample for measuring pure shear is only valid in the linear domain of stress-strain. In the non-linear domain the stress state is not a pure shear.

ANSWER:

Author agrees.

COMMENT: A. Rotem, Technion, Haifa

The shear strength measured from a $\pm 45^\circ$ flat specimen cannot be measured because of the combined stress field in the material which causes failure. Thus the true shear strength is much higher (by a factor of about 50%).

CHAIRMAN'S REMARK:

This observation supports my view, expressed earlier, that although the elastic properties of laminates are calculable from those of the constituent laminae, we must be much more careful when it comes to structure-sensitive properties such as strength or fatigue performance.

QUESTION: K.G. Wangberg, Technical Univ. of Linkoping, Sweden:

Did you experimentally verify that $X_4 = X_2$, and if so, how was this done?

ANSWER:

We did not verify this experimentally; however, a theoretical justification can be given as follows:

Consider a unidirectional composite such as that shown in Fig. 1 in our paper. If such a composite is loaded shear by σ_4 , then at failure the value of σ_4 defines X_4 .

Now consider the state of stress on an infinitesimal plane (of this unidirectional composite) in the 2-3 plane rotated at 45° from the original coordinate system of Fig. 1.

In the new coordinate system

$$\sigma_2' = -\sigma_3' = \sigma_4 \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Now failure due to σ_2' defines X_2 and failure due to σ_3' defines X_3 . Since typically $|X_2| \gg X_2$, the failure under the shear loading can alternatively be seen as a failure under the stress σ_2' . Hence from (1)

$$X_2 \approx \sigma_4 \Big|_{\text{at failure}} = X_4 \dots\dots\dots(2).$$

FIGURE 1

APPLICATION TO CONSTRUCTION,
TRANSPORTATION AND COMMUNICATION

GENEVA

L.N. Phillips, Chairman

BOSTON

E. Scala, Chairman

SELECTED PAPERS

R.W. Lewis
I. Wolock
B.R. Noton
G.A. Wilkins

CHAIRMAN'S SUMMARY REPORT

Session 8

by L. N. Phillips

This is the final session and it will be a crowded and important one.

Important, because it is concerned with applications and potential application of composites.

Crowded because, I am happy to say, engineers and scientists from every country are finding more sensible uses for these materials with each passing year.

This activity, the search for applications, is of the essence. It provides a technical challenge - leading to new design concepts, new forms of material and new fabrication methods. Also it increases the market so that production of reinforcing fibres, fillers and resins can be scaled up and their price brought down.

The successive reductions in price which take place during the development of a new material, make it possible to realize those further potential uses, which, for the moment, are in cold-storage.

Having found that the distinguished speakers for this morning's session had not been given precise speaking times, we undertook some hurried but friendly international negotiations.

This is how they turned out.

The four main US speakers, whose papers have been abstracted in your programme, will try to condense their remarks into 35 minutes each, give or take a little. Then, after the break, we shall move on to

the shorter contributions from the other speakers, which taken together will give us a bird's eye view of the European scene.

Should we run short of time - Noblesse oblige! and the Chairman will exercise his prerogative and cut short the contribution from the final speaker. . . . Meanwhile, it gives me great pleasure to introduce Dr. Bob Lewis for the first paper.

CHAIRMAN'S SUMMARY REPORT

Session 8

by Dr. E. Scala
P.O. Box 1362
Cortland, NY 13045

The broad and successful uses of high strength filament reinforced composite materials in aircraft, missiles, ships, engines, instruments, sporting equipment, etc., were well illustrated by the authors in this applications session. This closing series of papers and discussions topped off the many developments and applications covered in the previous three days of the conferences. Both development and production with the advanced fibers convincingly demonstrated military and commercial uses. Most important, they portend the coming applications in tonnage quantities to transportation, energy conversion, buildings, and special but critical items such as cables and ropes. When one adds to these the eutectic composites for high temperature components and electronic devices, the diversity and potentials for advanced composite materials can only lead to a broadening stream of technological developments, increasing investments in development, and the drive to decrease costs. The discussions questioned cost effectiveness, which is the key to tonnage applications.

The sessions lead by talks from U.S. Army and Navy technical laboratories, complimenting previous Air Force speakers, were broadened by the many countries summing up their activities and interests, plus the many questions indicating the international interest and potential. One concludes that in areas where high cost materials and structures have been justified, advanced composites have made great strides ranging from space aircraft to sporting equipment. The glass reinforced polymers have lead the way for the advanced composites in construction and transportation, but there is a long way to go.